

Supplementary Document

Pinostrobin pentanoate as a selective estrogen receptor- α antagonist in breast cancer: integrated *in silico* and *in vitro* evaluation

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Fig S1. IR spectrum of pinostrobin using FTIR-ATR

Fig S2. IR spectrum of pinostrobin pentanoate using FTIR-ATR

Fig S3. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz) spectrum of pinostrobin

Fig S4. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz) spectrum of pinostrobin

Fig S5. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz) spectrum of pinostrobin pentanoate

Fig S6. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz) spectrum of pinostrobin pentanoate

Fig S7. Mass spectrum of pinostrobin

Fig S8. Mass spectrum of pinostrobin pentanoate

Fig S9. Hydrogen bond variation throughout the molecular dynamic simulation of the Er α -ligand complexes. The plot illustrates the number of hydrogen bonds formed during the simulation. The result indicates the fluctuation and stability of hydrogen bonding interactions between (A) pinostrobin, (B) pinostrobin pentanoate, (C) doxorubicin, and the receptor during a 100 ns simulation.

Table S1. Comparison between this study and the previous study (Susilawati et al., 2024)

Aspect	Susilawati et al., 2024	This Study	Novel Improvement
Interaction similarity (%) in docking analysis	Not evaluated	Evaluated	New quantitative metric
Binding mode comparison	Qualitative only	Quantitative, similarity score	More precise comparison
MM-GBSA calculation	Not included	Included	Adds thermodynamic validation
H-bond Energy Analysis	Not reported	Reported	Provides interaction energy contribution